

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 15

The goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
Psa. 15:0 A Psalm of David.	
Psa. 15:1 O LORD, who may abide in Your tent?	1 מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד יְהוָה מִי־יָגוּר בְּאֹהֶל־ךָ מִי־יִשְׁכַּן בְּתֵר קְדוֹשְׁךָ :
Who may dwell on Your holy hill? 2 He who walks with integrity, and works righteousness, And speaks truth in his heart.	הוֹלֵךְ תְּמִים וּפְעֵל צְדָק וְדָבַר אֱמֻת בְּלִבָּבוֹ : 3 לֹא־רָגַל אֶעֱלֶה לְשִׁנוֹ לֹא־עָשִׂיה לְרַעְהוּ רָעָה
3 He does not slander ¹ with his tongue, Nor does evil to his neighbor, Nor takes up a reproach against his friend;	וְחִרְפָּה לֹא־נִשְׂאָ עַל־קַרְבּוֹ : 4 נִבְזָה אֲבַעֲיָנוּ נִמְאָס וְאֶת־יְרֵאֵי יְהוָה יַכְבֵּד נִשְׁבַּע לְהִרְעֹ וְלֹא יִמָּר : 5 כִּסְפוֹ אֲלֹא־נָתַן בְּנִשְׁפָּה וְשָׁחַד עַל־נַפְקֵי לֹא לָקַח עֲשֵׂה־אֱלֹהֵי לֹא יִמּוּט לְעוֹלָם :
4 In whose eyes a reprobate is despised, But who honors those who fear the LORD;	
He swears to his own hurt and does not change;	
5 He does not put out his money ¹ at interest, Nor does he take a bribe against the innocent.	
He who does these things will never be shaken.	

Targum

¹ A hymn of David. O LORD, who is worthy to dwell in your tabernacle, who is worthy to abide on the mountain of your sanctuary? ² One who walks in integrity, and does righteous deeds, and speaks truth in his heart. ³ He does not slander with his tongue, he causes no harm to his fellow, and he bears no shame against his neighbor. ⁴ Who despises the contemptible to his face, but honors those who fear the LORD; who will swear to do harm to himself and does not change. ⁵ He has not given his money at interest; he has not accepted a bribe against the innocent; one who does these things will never be moved.

Verse One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
Psa. 15:0 A Psalm of David.	1 מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד יְהוָה מִי־יָגוּר
Psa. 15:1 O LORD, who may abide in Your tent? Who may dwell on Your holy hill?	בְּאֵהֶלְךָ מִי־יִשְׁכַּן בְּתֵר קֹדְשְׁךָ :

Verse Analysis

Psalm 15 briefly outlines the requirements for a human to meet with God. Such a person could enter the tent of the LORD because he/she dedicated their entire life to the House of the LORD.

גִּיר (guir) means to abide, be gathered, be a stranger, dwell (in/with), gather together, remain, sojourn, inhabit, surely, continuing. This word is used when the journey is a short one.

One day all human beings will look to Mount Zion as the lofty center of the LORD's sanctuary on Earth.

The reference to the "tent" reminds the reader of the tent set up for the Ark of the Covenant. It sat under a tent covered with clothes until Solomon completed the LORD's house in Jerusalem.

The Holy Hill is a reference to Jerusalem.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A Psalm of David. LORD who shall sojourn in your Tabernacle. Who will dwell on Mount Zion in Your Temple?

Verse Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
2 He who walks with integrity, and works righteousness, And speaks truth in his heart.	הוֹלֵךְ תָּמִים וּפְעֵל צְדָק וְדָבָר אֱמֶת בְּלִבּוֹ :

Verse Analysis

הוֹלֵךְ תָּמִים (holech tameem) – this phrase means a "moral way of life" which is filled with high integrity and subordinates all physical and spiritual desires without reservation to the sovereignty of the moral law. This person controls physical sensuality. According to Hebraic truth, the physical, sensual bestiality expressions cannot exist with the spiritual elevation to the LORD. The LORD drives away immoral people from His house. This person also has honest dealings with his/her fellow person. A dishonest person cannot enter the house of the LORD. This person's words are always truth.

Morality, honesty, and truthfulness constitute the threefold requirement that the Sanctuary of the LORD's Law exacts anyone who wishes to travel in it, especially for the person who wishes to dwell on Mount Zion, the holy mountain.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The person who walks in moral integrity practices righteousness and must speak the truth in his/her heart.

Verse Three

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>³ He does not slander ¹with his tongue, Nor does evil to his neighbor, Nor takes up a reproach against his friend;</p>	<p>לֹא-רִגַּל עַל-לְשׁוֹנוֹ לֹא-עָשָׂה לְרֵעֵהוּ רָעָה</p>

Verse Analysis

עַל-לְשׁוֹנוֹ (al-leshonu) – this phrase refers to ideas that did not emanate from the speaker's mind but that of ideas derived from other sources.

The person who can enter the Temple was to be a person of inexplicable integrity and moral honesty.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Only a perfect person who never slanders never does evil to his fellow human, nor casts blame on anyone.

Verse Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁴ In whose eyes a reprobate is despised, But who honors those who fear the LORD; He swears to his own hurt and does not change;</p>	<p>נְבִיזָה אֲבַעֲיִנּוּ נִמְאָס וְאֶת־יְרֵאֵי⁴ יְהוָה יְכַבֵּד נִשְׁבַּע לְהָרַע וְלֹא יִמָּרֵד</p>

Verse Analysis

The Psalm is also referring to the interpersonal relations that every person has. These relationships are strengthened when a person lives a moral and ethical life. Relationships are built on truth. A person of high morals does not tell falsehoods about anything and especially anyone. It is this person that the LORD welcomes into His house.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The LORD does not like to see dishonorable persons. The LORD honors people who have reverence for Him. The LORD has sworn this to His people, and He does not change.

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁵ He does not put out his money ¹at interest, Nor does he take a bribe against the innocent. He who does these things will never be shaken.</p>	<p>כִּסְפוֹ אֵלֹא-נָתַן בְּנִשְׁךָ וְשִׁחַר עַל- נֶקִי לֹא לָקַח עֲשֵׂה-אֱלֹהִים לֹא יִמּוּט לְעוֹלָם :</p>

Verse Analysis

The description of this person is unselfish toward doing good for others. Indeed, this person thrives on doing good deeds.

The reference about the bribes is because, in ancient days, judges were not paid. They made their money by accepting bribes. It was not unusual for a rich man to bribe a judge to steal his neighbors land. Therefore, it was beneficial to settle any dispute outside of the justice system of the day.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The unselfish person who loans money without interest never takes a bribe against an innocent person and always lives by this code.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

A Psalm of David. LORD who shall sojourn in your Tabernacle. Who will dwell on Mount Zion in Your Temple?

The person who walks in moral integrity practices righteousness and must speak the truth in his/her heart.

Only a perfect person who never slanders never does evil to his fellow human, nor casts blame on anyone.

The LORD does not like to see dishonorable persons. The LORD honors people who have reverence for Him. The LORD has sworn this to His people, and He does not change.

The unselfish person who loans money without interest never takes a bribe against an innocent person and always lives by this code.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

